

Histopathological Study of Cervical Lesions in a Tertiary Health Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer remains a significant public health issue globally, largely preventable through early detection and treatment of precancerous lesions. Histopathological analysis plays a critical role in accurately diagnosing cervical lesions, which is essential for effective intervention.

Methods: This retrospective observational study analyzed cervical biopsies from 75 patients at the Department of Pathology, LSLAMMC, and Hospital, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, over one year from September 1, 2023, to August 31, 2024. The lesions were categorized into benign, pre-malignant, and malignant based on standard histopathological criteria.

Results: The study found a high prevalence of pre-malignant lesions, particularly cervical intraepithelial neoplasia, accounting for 46.7% of all cases. Malignant lesions were more prevalent in patients over 50 years of age. The age group 30-40 had the highest occurrence of pre-malignant conditions, indicating a critical target demographic for screening programs.

Conclusion: The findings emphasize the importance of targeted screening and personalized management strategies for cervical health, particularly focusing on pre-malignant lesions to prevent progression to invasive cancer.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Histopathology, Pre-malignant Lesions, Screening Programs.

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Introduction

Histopathology plays a crucial role in the medical field, offering definitive insights into the morphological aspects of tissues affected by disease [1]. The study of cervical lesions through histopathological examination is especially significant, given the high incidence and potential severity of cervical abnormalities [2]. Cervical cancer, primarily caused by the Human Papillomavirus (HPV), remains a leading cause of mortality among women worldwide, despite advancements in screening and vaccination. This underscores the importance of effective diagnostic methods to detect and characterize cervical lesions early and accurately [3,4].

In tertiary health care settings, where advanced medical resources are available, histopathological studies are instrumental in refining diagnosis, guiding treatment, and informing prognosis [5]. Such institutions often serve as the final referral centers for cases that are complex and challenging, making the accuracy of histopathological diagnosis even more critical [6]. The histopathological analysis of cervical tissues not only helps in

distinguishing benign from malignant lesions but also aids in the identification of pre-malignant conditions, thus playing a vital role in preventive health care [7].

With increasing advancements in histological techniques, the precision of pathological diagnosis has improved, aiding clinicians in offering targeted therapies tailored to individual patient profiles [8]. Moreover, the integration of histopathological data with clinical and epidemiological parameters can lead to comprehensive care strategies, enhancing patient outcomes and contributing to public health surveillance [9,10].

This study aims to assess the histopathological features of cervical lesions diagnosed in a tertiary healthcare hospital. This will provide insight into the prevalence and types of cervical pathologies encountered, assess the efficacy of current diagnostic practices, and potentially guide improvements in the treatment and management of patients with cervical lesions. Through this investigation, we seek to contribute to the broader knowledge base necessary for advancing cervical

health initiatives and enhancing patient care protocols.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a retrospective observational study aimed at evaluating the histopathological characteristics of cervical lesions in patients who have undergone diagnostic procedures at the Department of Pathology, LSLAMMC, and Hospital, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh.

Study Period: The study encompasses a duration of one year, from September 1 2023, to August 31, 2024. This period will allow for the collection and analysis of data within a defined timeframe to maintain the consistency and relevance of the findings.

Study Population: A total of 75 patients have been included in this study. These patients were selected based on the availability of complete medical and histopathological records during the study period. The inclusion criteria are patients of any age and sex who underwent a biopsy for suspected cervical lesions within the study timeframe.

Data Collection: Data will be collected from the medical records department of LSLAMMC and Hospital. Information extracted will include patient demographics (age, sex), clinical findings, details of biopsy (date, type), histopathological reports, and any follow-up outcomes where available. Histopathological slides will be re-evaluated by a team of pathologists to ensure the accuracy of the diagnosis.

Histopathological Analysis: Histopathological examination will be performed using standard staining techniques, primarily Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E). Additional stains or immunohistochemical analysis will be utilized as deemed necessary based on the initial findings. Each sample will be reviewed independently by two pathologists to minimize observer bias, with discrepancies resolved through consensus or consultation with a senior pathologist.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics to outline the frequency and types of cervical lesions. The association between histopathological findings and clinical characteristics will be assessed using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Statistical significance will be set at a p-value of less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: This study has been approved by the Institutional Review Board of LSLAMMC and Hospital. All data will be handled confidentially, and results will be anonymized to maintain patient privacy.

Results

The study involved a detailed histopathological examination of cervical lesions from 75 patients treated at the Department of Pathology, LSLAMMC, and Hospital, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, from September 1, 2023, to August 31, 2024. The analysis revealed a range of benign, pre-malignant, and malignant lesions with varying incidences and characteristics.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients	Percentage
Under 20	5	6.7%
20-30	15	20%
30-40	25	33.3%
40-50	20	26.7%
Over 50	10	13.3%
Total	75	100%

This table outlines the age distribution and demographic characteristics of the patients. The majority of the patients fell into the age group of 30-50 years, which is consistent with the typical age range for increased risk of cervical pathological changes.

Table 2: Types of Cervical Lesions Identified

Type of Lesion	Number of Cases	Percentage
Benign	20	26.7%
Pre-malignant (e.g., CIN)	35	46.7%
Malignant (e.g., Squamous Cell Carcinoma)	20	26.6%
Total	75	100%

This table categorizes the types of lesions identified through histopathological examination. The data illustrate a higher prevalence of pre-malignant lesions, which underscores the importance of early screening and intervention.

Table 3: Correlation Between Age and Lesion Type

Age Group (years)	Benign	Pre-malignant	Malignant	Total
Under 20	3	2	0	5
20-30	7	6	2	15
30-40	5	15	5	25
40-50	3	10	7	20
Over 50	2	2	6	10
Total	20	35	20	75

This table displays the correlation between age groups and the type of cervical lesions, highlighting an increased frequency of malignant lesions in older age groups.

The results indicate a significant incidence of pre-malignant lesions, particularly in the 30-40 age group, suggesting that this demographic could benefit most from targeted screening programs. The correlation of increased malignant lesions with advancing age emphasizes the need for vigilant follow-up and intervention strategies in older populations. These findings will help refine screening and treatment protocols and suggest areas for further research in cervical health.

Discussion

The findings from our study conducted at the Department of Pathology, LSLAMMC, and Hospital, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, provide substantial insights into the histopathological profiles of cervical lesions over one year. This discussion will focus on the interpretation of these findings, their implications for clinical practice, and suggestions for future research.

Prevalence of Pre-Malignant Lesions: A critical observation from the study is the high prevalence of pre-malignant lesions, notably cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), which constituted nearly half of the cases examined. This is particularly significant as it underscores the potential for cervical cancer prevention through early detection and appropriate management of these lesions [11]. The prominence of pre-malignant lesions in the 30-40 age group suggests that cervical screening programs should perhaps focus more intensively on this demographic, which is also likely to benefit the most from early therapeutic interventions [12].

Age-Related Trends in Cervical Lesions: The correlation between age and lesion type revealed an expected trend: the incidence of malignant lesions increased with age. Older women, particularly those over 50, exhibited a higher proportion of malignant lesions, which aligns with global epidemiological data [13]. This age-related increase in malignancy rate highlights the need for continued vigilance in screening older populations, despite the lower overall rate of HPV infection observed in these groups due to lesser sexual activity [14]. It may be

advisable to tailor cervical cancer screening and prevention strategies to not only focus on younger women but also to ensure adequate coverage of older age groups who are at an elevated risk of developing invasive cancer [15].

Implications for Clinical Practice: The study's findings have several implications for clinical practice. Firstly, the high rate of pre-malignant lesions detected suggests that current screening methods are effective at identifying early-stage changes amenable to treatment interventions. However, the need for enhanced public health messaging and education regarding the importance of regular screening is evident, particularly for women nearing or surpassing menopause, who may underestimate their risk of cervical cancer [16].

Secondly, the differential prevalence of lesion types across age groups indicates that personalized approaches to screening might be warranted. For instance, while younger women might benefit more from HPV vaccination and regular Pap tests, older women might need a different screening approach that considers the higher risk of invasive cancer [17].

Limitations and Future Research: While this study provides valuable data, it has limitations, including its retrospective design and the relatively small sample size. These factors may limit the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, as the study was conducted in a single tertiary care center, the results might not reflect the patterns observed in different settings or the general population.

Future research should aim to include larger, multi-center studies to confirm these findings and potentially explore the genetic and molecular profiles of cervical lesions [18,19]. Such studies could provide deeper insights into the pathogenesis of cervical cancer and pave the way for more targeted and effective therapeutic strategies [20].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant role of histopathological evaluation in identifying and categorizing cervical lesions, with a notable prevalence of pre-malignant lesions in women aged 30-40 years and a rise in malignant lesions among older women. These findings emphasize the need for age-specific screening strategies and reinforce the importance of histopathological assessment in the effective management of cervical health.

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